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**INDO AMERICAN
 JOURNAL OF
 PHARMACEUTICAL
 RESEARCH**

Evaluation of *Heteropogon contortus* (L.) Beauv. Methanolic extract for Mast cell, Cell Membrane and free radical stabilization

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history
 Received 12 Oct 2012
 Available online 26 Oct 2012

Keywords
Heteropogon contortus,
 antioxidant, mast cell
 stabilization, membrane
 stabilization

ABSTRACT

Methanolic extract of *Heteropogon contortus* (L.) Beauv was screened for mast cell stabilization (in vitro anti-histaminic) and membrane stabilization (in vitro anti-inflammatory) effects. Extracts was also evaluated for antioxidant effect (DPPH, % RRI of DPPH, reducing power and metal chelation). In addition extract was standardized using chromatographic fingerprinting and spectroscopic quantitation for phytoconstituents contents. HC-ME exhibited good anti-hisatminic effect in by reducing histamine release quantity from C-48/80 induced mast cells destabilization. Stabilizes hypotonic and heat induced destabilized cell membrane. Findings of the above studies helps to reveals that, HC-ME not only exhibit antioxidant activity but also exhibit membrane and mast cell stabilization potential.

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Please cite this article in press as Mahavir H. Ghante et.al. Evaluation of *Heteropogon contortus* (L.) Beauv. Methanolic extract for Mast cell, Cell Membrane and free radical stabilization. Indo American Journal of Pharm Research.2012:2(10).

INTRODUCTION

Heteropogon contortus (L.) Beauv. ex Roem. and Schult. Synonym *Andropogon contortus* L. belonging to the Family Poaceae (alt. Gramineae) **HC**. The grass is commonly known as common spear grass, black spear grass, bellary grass, *Kher* (Hindi), *Gantegawata* (Marathi). Its native distribution encompasses southern Asia, southern Africa and Northern Australia. The species has also become a naturalised weed in tropical and subtropical regions in Asia and the east Americans (Bhatt et al, 2006).

Dabadghao and Shankarnarayan (1970) have reported the crude protein content in Indian species. Grass is also reported to contain myo-inositol, galactinol, and raffinose It is reported to contain polysaccharide (Blake et al 170; Beveridge et al 1972). Roots have been reported to have diuretic and stimulant properties. Plants also reported to found useful in toothache, fever, atrophy, emaciation or cachexy, muscular pain, hematological disorders, dysentery and scorpion sting (Chopra and Nayar, 1956). It is ethnopharmacologically used for asthma in the form of extracts or steam distillation product of whole plant (Kirtikar and Basu, 1935). Oil distilled from the awns has been found useful in asthma. However, preclinical as well as experimental data showing anti histaminic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant potential of HC have not been found to the best of our knowledge. Therefore the present investigation was undertaken to evaluate mast cell, membrane stabilizing and antioxidant effects of HC-ME.

COLLECTION AND AUTHENTICATION OF *Heteropogon contortus*

Heteropogon contortus (Linn.) P. Beauv. ex Roem. and Schult. grass, belongs to the family Poaceae; were collected from the campus of Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University campus, Nagpur as well as outskirts of Nagpur District, India, and authenticated from Botanical Survey of India, Pune, India. [Reference No. BSI/WC/Identi./Tech./2008/473 and 272].

EXTRACTION OF HC GRASS

Coarse powder (500 g) of HC was exhaustively defatted using pet ether (60-80⁰) and then extracted with methanol using Soxhlet apparatus to obtain HC-PE and HC-ME respectively Extracts were concentrated, filtered through Whatmann filter paper 41 and stored in air tight container placed in vacuum desiccator for future use.

Table 1 Percentage yield and weight of HC extracts

Plant material	HC whole plant	
	HC- ME	HC -PE
Extracts obtained		
Weight of extracts (g)	11.56	7.6
% Yield	2.89	0.19

PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION AND STANDARDIZATION

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

All the extracts were screened for presence of phytoconstituents viz alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, saponins, triterpenoids, proteins and sugars (Trease and Evans, 1983) Table 2.

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) analysis of extracts

Chromatographic fingerprinting was carried out using silica gel G as stationary phase and different solvent combinations as mobile phase to identify and confirm the presence of major phytoconstituents (polyphenols, triterpenoids and steroids etc). Solution of HC-ME (1 mg/ml) in required amount (4-8 μ l) was applied on the TLC plates. Developed TLC plates were observed with various derivatizing reagents (FeCl_3 , 10% H_2SO_4 , and vanillin- H_2SO_4) and R_f values of observed spots were recorded (Harbone, 1973) Table 3.

Table 2
Phytochemical screening of HC extracts

Extract	Flavonoids	Alkaloids	Carbohydrates	Saponin	Tannins	Steroids	Triterpenoids
HC-PE	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
HC-ME	-	-	+	+	-	+	++

(+) indicate presence of phytoconstituent and (-) indicate absence of phytoconstituent

Table 3: TLC fingerprinting of methanolic extract of HC

Extract	Mobile Phase	R_f Values	Derivatizing reagent
HC-ME	CH:ME(1.8:0.2)	0.11, 0.25, 0.43, 0.58, 0.92	10 % H_2SO_4

Phytochemical standardization of extracts

Determination of total carbohydrate content:

Phenol-sulfuric acid quantitative colorimetric method was implemented for the quantization of total carbohydrates from the HC-ME (Rao and Pattabiraman, 1989). HC-ME (100 μ g/ml) or glucose (to get calibration curve) in different concentration in 5 μ l increments (5-50 μ l) was mixed with phenol solution (500 μ l) and H_2SO_4 (2.5 ml; 96%). The mixture was allowed to equilibrate and for color development for 5-10 min. The absorbance of colored solution was measured at 490 nm against prepared blank. Carbohydrate contents of extracts were calculated from the corrected absorbances obtained from the calibration curve of glucose. The amount of sugar present was determined by using regression equation obtained from calibration curve of glucose ($R^2 = 0.9912$), Results are given in Table 4.

Absorbance $y = 0.0255$ [Glucose (μ g)] $x + 0.0032$

Determination of total saponins

Isolation of crude saponins

HC-ME (10 g) was taken with 20% ethanol (100 ml) and stirred for 10-12 h at 55 $^{\circ}$ C. Obtained extract was filtered through Whatman filter paper and residue was re extracted with 20% ethanol (200 ml). Obtained extract were combined, reduced up to 40 ml and extracted with diethyl ether (20 X 03) to obtain colorless aqueous

extract. The pH of aqueous extract was adjusted to about 4.5 and solution was further extracted with n-butanol (20 X 03). The butanolic extract was washed with NaCl (5%, 20 X 03) and finally evaporated on water bath in fume cupboard. Obtained residue was measured and calculated as % weight as compared to crude extract. The content was expressed as purified saponin equivalent (PSE). Crude saponin 1 ml (100 µg/ml) or saponin purified (1 ml; 100 µg/ml) in different concentration was used for further determination.

Determination of total saponin content

Crude saponin solution (1 ml; 100 µg/ml) or saponin purified (1 ml; in different concentration 10-100 µg/ml) was vortexed with 5 ml of vanillin H₂SO₄ solution (0.7% vanillin; 65% H₂SO₄ and volume was adjusted to 100 ml methanol). The reaction mixture was maintained at 60±2⁰C in water bath for 1 h. Reaction mixture was cooled and absorbance was measured at 472 nm against prepared blank. The saponin content of crude saponin was calculated and expressed as purified saponin equivalent (PSE) from the equation obtained from calibration curve drawn using purified saponin (R² = 0.9974) (Ukpabi et al, 2003), Results are given in Table 4.

$$\text{Absorbance (y)} = 0.0027 [\text{PSE } (\mu\text{g})] \text{ x } + 0.0007$$

Table 4
Spectrophotometric standardization of methanolic extract of HC

Extract	Total carbohydrate content	Total Saponin content
HC-ME	3.08 ± 0.39	0.92 ± 0.20

Values represent the mean ± S. D. of three independent replicates

EVALUATION OF ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY

Evaluation of scavenging activity on DPPH radicals

HC-ME or standard solution 1 ml (10-50 µg/ml) was added separately to 2 ml of DPPH in methanol (100 mM). After incubation at 37⁰C for 30 min, the final volume was made up to 4 ml with methanol and the absorbance of individual reaction mixture was determined at 517 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The corresponding blank readings were also taken and the known radical scavenger, ascorbic acid was used as a positive control. Percent inhibition was calculated by comparing the absorbance values of control and test extract (Chu et al, 2000) using formula; % Inhibition = [(A₀-A₁)/A₀] x 100, Where, A₀ -absorbance of the control reaction solution and A₁ - absorbance in the presence of the test extracts or standard (Table 5).

Determination of percentage residual rate of inhibition (%RRI)

The HC-ME (1 ml, 100 µg/ ml dissolved in methanol) was added to the mixture of phosphate buffer (4 ml; 1M, pH 5.5) and DPPH (4 ml; 1.25 X 10⁻⁴M). The solution was mixed well and kept for standing in dark for 5 min and finally volume was made up to 10 ml with methanol. After 0.5, 1, 3 and 7 h absorbance of the mixture was recorded at 520 nm (Yamasaki et al, 1994) (Table 5). The percentage residual rate of inhibition (%RRI) was calculated using formula

$$\text{RRI} = (\text{Abs } t_0) - (\text{Abs } t_x) / (\text{Abs } t_0) \times 100 \text{ Where, Abs } t_0 - \text{absorbance at time interval 0 min and Abs } t_x - \text{absorbance at specific time interval.}$$

Determination of reducing power

HC-ME (1 ml; 25-125 µg/ml) was mixed with phosphate buffer (2.5 ml, 0.2 M, pH 6.6) and potassium ferricyanide (2.5 ml; 1%). The mixture was incubated at 50⁰C for 20 min. To the resultant solution tricarboxylic

acid (TCA) (2.5 ml; 10%) was mixed well and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 min. Afterwards, 2.5 ml of supernatant was added to FeCl₃ (0.5 ml; 0.1%) and distilled water (2.5 ml). The absorbance of prepared reaction mixture was recorded at 700 nm (Oyaizu M, 1986). Increased reducing power was indicated by increased absorbance of the reaction mixture (Table 5).

Determination of ferrous metal ion chelating activity

Test extract (2.5 ml; 25-125 µg/ml) was mixed well with FeCl₂ (0.5 ml, 5 mM) resultant mixture was kept standing for 10 min at room temperature to achieve the equilibrium. The absorbance of obtained solution was recorded at 562 nm using UV-visible spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition of ferrozine -Fe²⁺ complex was measured and calculated by following formula (Ilhami et al, 2005). % Inhibition was calculated using formula % Inhibition = [(A₀-A₁)/A₀] X 100 Where, A₀ -absorbance of the control solution, A₁ -absorbance in the presence of the test extracts or standard (Table 5).

Table 5: Effect of HC extract on % RRI of DPPH, % DPPH inhibition, reducing power, and % metal chelation

% RRI at (h)	% RRI		% DPPH Inhibition			Reducing power			% Metal Chelation	
	AA	HC-ME	Conc. (µg/ml)	Ascorbic Acid	HC-ME	Conc. (µg/ml)	AA	HC-ME	EDTA	HC-ME
0.5	98.73 ±1.44	44.71 ±1.56	10	22.57 ±0.99	16.21 ±1.96	25	0.294 ±0.076	0.097 ±0.008	28.12 ±0.19	07.49 ± 1.07
1	83.45 ±1.73	37.89 ±2.15	20	36.41 ±1.26	23.87 ±1.25	50	0.413 ±0.098	0.143 ±0.092	57.22 ±1.04	17.11 ± 1.54
3	71.19 ±0.78	21.46 ±2.08	30	49.33 ±1.54	37.31 ±1.14	75	0.682 ±0.128	0.271 ±0.085	79.16 ±1.29	25.16 ± 1.18
7	59.16 ±1.29	08.11 ±1.68	40	61.89 ±1.08	57.33 ±2.71	100	0.841 ±0.109	0.342 ±0.098	91.81 ±2.18	40.03 ± 1.61
			50	76.23 ±0.84	69.08 ±1.39	125	1.095 ±0.153	0.516 ±0.112	98.68 ±2.11	54.32 ± 2.34

Values represent the mean ± S. D. of three independent replicates

Inhibition of Histamine Release from Rat Peritoneal Mast Cells

Preparation of rat peritoneal mast cell (RPMCs)

Rats were exsanguinated and injected with Hank's Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) in abdominal cavity. The abdomen was gently massaged for 120 sec and cavity was opened to aspirate the fluid containing peritoneal cell. Peritoneal fluid was centrifuged at 2000 rpm to obtain cell components, a buffy mass, which was resuspended in HBSS. Resultant cell suspension was treated for separating mast cells from other components (i.e. macrophages and small lymphocytes) by suspending peritoneal cells in 1 ml of HBSS which was layered on 2 ml of 0.225 g/ml metrizamide (density 1.120 g/ml) and centrifuged at room temperature for 15 min at 3000 rpm. The cells remaining at the buffer-metrizamide interface were aspirated and discarded; the cells in the pellet were washed and resuspended in 10 ml of HBSS. The obtained suspension was considered as mast cell suspension (Vogel, 2002).

MEASUREMENT OF HISTAMINE RELEASE FROM RPMC

To test extract in different concentrations or disodium cromoglycate (DSCG) (1 ml; 10-100 µg/ml) was mixed with mast cell suspension and incubated at 37 °C for 15 min in separate test tubes. Each mixture thus obtained was made up to 3 ml with HBSS, to this an equal volume (3 ml) of compound 48/80 [C-48/80] (10^{-6} g/ml) was added and allowed to incubate at 37 °C for 30 min followed by centrifugation at 2500 rpm for 5 min. Top layer of the resulting solution from each test tube was transferred to the tube containing 300 mg NaCl and 1.25 ml n-butanol. This solution was alkalized by adding 3 N NaOH (1 ml) to extract histamine into n-butanol. After shaking, the sample was centrifuged for 5 min at 2000 rpm and 1 ml of the top layer (n-butanol) was separated and mixed well with 2 ml of n-heptane and 0.4 ml of 0.12 N HCl. The test tubes content was mixed and allowed to stand for obtaining organic and aqueous phase, 0.5 ml of the aqueous phase was then transferred to another test tube. To each tube containing aqueous phase, 1 N NaOH (100 µl) and 0.2% o-phthalaldehyde (OPT) (100 µl) was added immediately under constant stirring. To this mixture 3 N HCl (100 µl) was added after 2 min and finally histamine concentration was determined from resultant reaction mixtures by using spectrofluorometer with excitation and emission wave lengths of 350 and 450 nm respectively results are given in Table 06. The different test and control solutions required for analysis were prepared in the following manner

1. Spontaneous histamine release- containing mast cells and solutions used to determine baseline,
2. Histamine release: solution contains mast cells and C-48/80 (10^{-6} g/ml),
3. Test compound control: contains solutions and test compound and

Percent histamine release inhibition (% HRI) from mast cells was determined by the following formula

$$\% \text{ HRI} = (\text{Sample HR} - \text{spontaneous HR}) / (100 \% \text{ HR} - \text{spontaneous HR}) \times 100$$

Where, % HRI- Histamine release Inhibition HR - Histamine release.

Table 6: Effect of HC extract on percent histamine release

Treatment	Effect on % HRI at different concentration (µg/ml)			
	10	25	50	100
DSCG	97.56±2.24	75.64±2.86*	34.22±2.10**	01.68± 1.07**
HC-ME	98.12±1.80	89.06±1.21*	73.81±1.34*	45.48 ±1.65*

Each value is presented as the mean ± S. D. of three independent determinations. Statistical significance was assessed using a one-way ANOVA with Bonferroni multiple comparison test: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.001

MEMBRANE STABILIZATION STUDY

Preparation of erythrocyte suspension

Blood was collected from the healthy Albino rats from the retro orbital plexus under light ether anesthesia using heparin as an anticoagulant and washed thrice with normal saline (NS). Total volume of saline was measured and reconstituted as a 40% v/v suspension with isotonic phosphate buffer solution (IPB), pH 7.4 (NaH₂PO₄. 2 H₂O, 0.26 g; Na₂HPO₄, 1.15 g; NaCl, 9 g, 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer). The obtained suspension was considered as erythrocyte cell suspension.

Effect on stabilization and lysis of erythrocytes

Test extracts (100 and 200 µg/ml) or standard drug acetyl salicylic acid (50 µg/ml) solution was prepared in IPB and taken in duplicate sets of centrifuge tubes. The test or standard solution (in 5 ml IPB) or vehicle (control group) was mixed with erythrocyte suspension. One set of tube was incubated for 20 min at 54°C in a thermostat water bath, while another was maintained at 0-5°C in an ice bath. The reaction mixture was centrifuged for 3 min at 3000 rpm, obtained supernatant was subjected for measurement of absorbance at 540 nm.

Effect on Hypotonic solution-induced haemolysis

Test extracts (100 and 200 µg/ml) or standard drug acetyl salicylic acid (50 µg/ml) solution was prepared in hypotonic solution [56 mM NaCl in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer (pH 7.4)] and mixed with erythrocyte stock suspension (30 µl). Whereas the control solution is test extract free solution. The mixtures were incubated at room temperature for 10 min and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 3 min and finally the absorbance of the obtained supernatant was measured at 540 nm. % Inhibition of haemolysis was calculated using formula (Shinde et al, 1999) (Table 7).

$$\% \text{ Inhibition of haemolysis} = 100 \times [1 - (\text{OD}_2 - \text{OD}_1) / (\text{OD}_3 - \text{OD}_1)]$$

Where,

OD₁. Absorbance of test sample unheated or in isotonic solution;

OD₂ - Absorbance of test sample heated or in hypotonic solution; and

OD₃ - Absorbance of control sample heated or in hypotonic solution.

Table 07: Effect of HC extracts and acetyl salicylic acid on heat- induced and hypotonic solution-induced haemolysis of erythrocyte membrane

Treatment	Conc (µg/ml)	% Inhibition of haemolysis	
		Heat-induced	Hypotonic solution-induced
HC-ME	100	08.73 ± 1.32*	05.27 ± 2.15
	200	13.89 ± 1.96*	09.26 ± 1.83
Acetyl salicylic acid	50	19.46 ± 1.45*	18.13 ± 2.54*

Values represent the mean ± S. D. of three independent replicates. *p < 0.05 and **p < 0.001 indicates the different levels of significance when compared against control group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

When methanolic extract of HC was subjected to preliminary phytochemical analysis, extract showed presence of saponin, steroids and triterpenoids. A result of TLC fingerprinting analysis was in accordance with the results of phytochemical screening showing presence of presence of steroids and triterpenoids. HC extract was standardized using spectrophotometric methods for quantization and determination of content of total saponins and carbohydrates. Total saponin content found in HC-ME was 0.92, whereas total carbohydrate content was found to be 3.08.

Chromatographic fingerprinting and spectroscopic standardization provides approach to appraise the quality of the herbal material of concern and caters quality parameter which may be useful in quality control processing such as extraction process of herbal drugs, which has gained intense interest recently (Liang Z Y et al, 2004; Handa 2004). HC-ME was screened for pharmacological profile using in vitro methods. Extract was evaluated for free radical scavenging, mast cell stabilization (in vitro anti-histamine activity) and membrane stabilization (in vitro anti-inflammatory activity) as an attempt to establish preliminary pharmacological effect of HC extract. Cascade of complex biochemical reactions many times resulted in production of reactive species (reactive oxygen as well as reactive nitrogen species) in biological systems. In addition, degeneration of defense system, diseased conditions and immunological factors which causes imbalance between oxidant or pro oxidant and defense system resulting excess production of radicals. Such excess of reactive species in the body can trigger chronic inflammatory disorders including pulmonary and rheumatic diseases. Oxidative stress can be counteracted by antioxidant effect produced by mediating single or in combination of the following mechanism viz. by capacity to cause reduction, chelation of catalytic transitional metal ions and decomposition of peroxides, inhibition of continued hydrogen abstraction with further perturbation of chain initiation. To understand the means of mechanism of antioxidant behavior single method cannot be helpful, therefore, among the several methods reported, antioxidant effects of HC-ME have been evaluated using different oxidant-antioxidant systems viz., DPPH scavenging, percent residual rate of inhibition (% RRI) of DPPH, reducing power and metal chelating effect (Shahidi et al 1992; Sanchez et al, 1999; Soares et al, 1997). HC-ME exhibited reduction of pink colored free radical 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) to the yellow-colored diphenyl picryl hydrazine at varied extents which was measured as absorbance's, calculated and expressed as percentage inhibition. % Inhibition possessed by standard antioxidant ascorbic acid and HC-ME at 50 µg/ml was found to be 76.23 and 69.08 respectively (Table 5). Evaluation of % RRI of DPPH helps to measure the ability of test extracts to scavenge radicals at different time interval such as 0.5, 1, 3 and 7 h (Yamasaki et al, 1994). HC-ME showed % RRI of 44.71% (at 0.5 h), followed by 08.11 at 7th h. Suggesting the ability of HC-ME to scavenge the free radical and protecting biological component from invading action of free radicals for longer duration (Table 5).

DPPH assay is one of the widely accepted and commonly used models to evaluate antioxidant activity in a relatively short time as compared to other methods (Soares et al, 1997). Measurement of percentage RRI is another method which measures the ability of test compounds or extracts to scavenge radicals and to protect biological system at different time interval (Yamasaki et al 1994). The metal chelating capacities were also calculated and expressed as percentage inhibition. For EDTA and HC-ME % inhibition were found to be 98.68 and 54.32 % respectively at 125 µg/ml. This antioxidant observation was found to be in accordance with the results obtained in previous antioxidant methods (Table 5). Metal chelator also implies the fact that, it exhibits property to reduce oxidative stress caused by metal generated radicals and pollutants (Leopoldini et al, 2006, Gordon, 1996).

Reducing ability of test extracts was evaluated on the basis of inhibition of Fe^{3+} - Fe^{2+} transformation system and monitored on the basis of change in absorbance of reaction mixture as increase in reducing power was indicated by increase in absorbance (Meir et al, 1995). HC extract may act by donating electron which reduces the oxidized intermediates of lipid per oxidation processes and thus considered as primary and secondary antioxidants. The reduction potential observed was in the order of ascorbic acid>HC-ME with absorbance's of 1.095 and, 0.516 respectively at the concentration of 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (Table 5).

All these in vitro antioxidant studies implies the high positive correlation between strong phytochemical profile of HC extract, by contributing through various mechanisms and revealing the varied antioxidant ability extracts. The antioxidants potential exhibited by HC-ME encompasses the different worthy properties, such as scavenging of reactive species for short as well as long period (DPPH inhibition and % RRI), stabilization of the of free radicals, reduction of reactive species and metal chelation. Which suggests HC-ME may provide improved protection to biological system against various radicals.

The inhibitory effect of HC-ME and standard drug, disodium cromoglycate (DSCG) on compound 48/80 (C-48/80) induced histamine releases from rat peritoneal mast cell (RPMC) was expressed as percent histamine release inhibition. HC plant extract and DSCG in the concentration range of 10-100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ exhibited dose dependent stabilization of mast cells along with decrease in histamine release from RPMC (Table 06). At 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ DSCG and HC-ME exhibited 01.68 and 45.48 % inhibition of histamine release. Least amount of percent histamine release suggests better potential to stabilize mast cells. HC-ME has shown presence of triterpenoids which have been reported to posses ability decrease histamine release from RPMC (Kim et al, 2006).

The effect of test compounds or extracts on destabilized mast cell mediators such as histamine can best be studied with the help of interaction of C-48/80 and RPMC. C-48/80 is a cationic amphiphile used to study effects on mast cell stabilization, due to its ability to induce degranulation of mast cells (Toda et al, 1988; Wu et al, 1993). The histamine concentration can be determined with the o-phthalaldehyde reaction (Vogel 2002).

Mast cells are the predominant inflammatory cell type localized in the airways of asthmatic patients. The interaction of mast cells constituents and airway smooth muscles suggest that mast cell contents are imperative contributors to airway hyper responsiveness in asthma. Immunological as well as non immunological factors may trigger the destabilization of mast cells and further release of inflammatory mediators (e.g. histamine and cytokines) which initiate the pathophysiology of inflammation and immediate hypersensitivity. Release of these mediators is accountable for the various adaptations at tissue level viz. bronchoconstriction, chemo taxis and increased vascular permeability along with adverse effect on growth and functioning of airway smooth muscles (Mekori and Metcalfe, 2000). Thus substance which exhibit mast cell stabilizing ability, have been proved useful to circumvent resulting pathological conditions occur due to release of mast cell contents.

HC extract showed percent inhibition of heat induced and hypotonic solution induced haemolysis. HC-ME exhibited 13.89 and 09.26, at 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, while acetyl salicylic acid exhibited 19.46 and 18.13 respectively in heat induced and hypotonic solution induced haemolysis models (Table 07). This supports to the antioxidant and mast cell stabilization potential of the active extracts. The extracts exhibited membrane stabilization effect by inhibiting heat and hypo tonicity induced lyses of erythrocyte membrane. The erythrocyte membrane is analogous to the lysosomal membrane (Chou, 1997) and its stabilization implies that the extract may stabilize lysosomal membranes. Stabilization of lysosomal membrane is important in limiting the inflammatory response by preventing the release of lysosomal constituents of activated neutrophil such as bactericidal enzymes and proteases, which cause further tissue inflammation and damage upon extra cellular release (Murugasan et al, 1981). The extract may inhibit the processes of lysis, and thus inhibiting the efflux of intracellular components which may cause damage to other cell components (Iwueke et al 2006).

To conclude, result obtained from above findings suggests the possible role of HC plant extract for the treatment of pathologies caused by mast cell destabilization, membrane destabilization and free radical generation, which mainly include acute and chronic inflammatory response such as asthma, arthritis, cardiovascular and neuronal diseases. As HC extract prevents destabilization of mast cells and hence further release of histamine. HC extract also inhibit pro-inflammatory conditions such as membrane destabilization and reduces oxidative burden. Study related to detailed evaluation of extracts, fractions or specific active constituent(s) for complete understanding of mechanism and related effects is in progress at our research laboratories.

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